

Systematic Review of Deep Learning and Vision Transformer Approaches for Brain Tumor Detection Using MRI Images

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 29 October 2025	Detecting brain tumors at an early stage through Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is essential for timely treatment and better survival outcomes. With the rapid progress of artificial intelligence, deep learning methods particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs) are increasingly used to automate tumor analysis by extracting features directly from MRI scans. This review evaluates 25 peer-reviewed articles published between 2019 and 2025 that applied these models for tumor detection, segmentation, and classification. Most studies show CNNs as the preferred choice, often reporting diagnostic accuracies above 90%. However, emerging evidence indicates that ViTs perform competitively, and sometimes better, on large-scale datasets due to their capacity to model global spatial relations through attention mechanisms. Despite these advances, issues such as small or unbalanced datasets, high computational requirements, overfitting, and limited interpretability remain barriers to clinical use. This paper summarizes key methodological developments, compares CNN and ViT performance, and highlights current obstacles. It concludes with practical recommendations for creating more robust and clinically relevant systems.
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KEYWORDS: Brain tumor, deep learning, convolutional neural networks, vision transformers, medical imaging	

I. INTRODUCTION

Brain tumors are severe neurological conditions caused by abnormal cell growth within the brain or its surrounding structures. Timely and accurate diagnosis is critical for treatment planning and improving survival [1]. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is the most widely used diagnostic tool due to its high soft-tissue contrast and non-invasive nature [2]. However, manual interpretation of MRI scans is time-intensive and can vary between radiologists, motivating the shift toward automated analysis [3].

Artificial intelligence (AI), and more specifically deep learning, has transformed the way medical images are analyzed. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been particularly successful, as they automatically learn hierarchical features from images, outperforming traditional machine learning approaches that rely on handcrafted features [4], [5].

Recently, Vision Transformers (ViTs) have emerged as an alternative to CNNs. Unlike CNNs, which capture mainly

local features, ViTs employ self-attention to model global spatial patterns within images [6]. This characteristic makes them useful for complex brain tumor analysis, where tumors vary greatly in size, location, and shape. Early applications show that ViTs can achieve results on par with or better than CNNs when trained on sufficiently large and diverse MRI datasets [7].

Nonetheless, deep learning applications face challenges such as small sample sizes, inconsistencies across MRI acquisition protocols, class imbalance, and overfitting [8]. High computational demands and limited model transparency also slow their adoption in clinical practice [9], [10].

This review brings together findings from 25 peer-reviewed studies published between 2019 and 2025, with a special focus on comparing CNNs and ViTs in brain tumor detection. Unlike earlier reviews that emphasized CNNs alone, this work highlights both models' strengths, limitations, and hybrid solutions. The contributions of this paper are:

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- A synthesis of CNN- and ViT-based methods for brain tumor detection, segmentation, and classification.
- A comparative evaluation of performance, datasets, and methodological strategies.
- Recommendations to enhance robustness, generalizability, and clinical relevance of AI-driven diagnostic systems.

By providing this comparative perspective, the review aims to inform future research and support the translation of AI models into real-world neuro-oncology.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Search Strategy

This review followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines [11] to ensure systematic reporting. Six major electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, Web of Science, and IEEE Xplore were searched for relevant articles. These platforms were chosen because they host large collections of peer-reviewed research across medical imaging, computer vision, and artificial intelligence.

The search used keyword combinations such as “*brain tumor*,” “*MRI*,” “*deep learning*,” “*convolutional neural networks*,” “*vision transformers*,” and “*tumor detection*,” linked with Boolean operators (AND/OR). To maintain focus on recent developments, only papers published between 2019 and 2025 were considered. In addition to database queries, the reference lists of retrieved papers and related reviews were manually screened to capture additional eligible studies.

B. Eligibility Criteria

To ensure the quality of evidence, the following inclusion criteria were applied:

- The study had to be published in a peer-reviewed journal or conference and written in English.
- Research must involve deep learning methods (CNNs, ViTs, or hybrid approaches) applied to brain tumor detection, segmentation, or classification from MRI datasets.
- The work had to report quantitative performance metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision, F1-score, or Dice similarity coefficient.
- Studies needed to provide adequate methodological detail for cross-comparison.

Exclusion criteria included:

- Research unrelated to brain tumor analysis.
- Studies not using MRI data.
- Papers without reported performance results.
- Non-peer-reviewed works such as dissertations, preprints, or abstracts without full text.

These criteria were applied to ensure that only reliable and comparable studies were included in the review.

C. Data Extraction

The screening was independently performed by two reviewers. Titles and abstracts were first checked against the eligibility criteria, and potentially relevant works were reviewed in full text. Disagreements were resolved by discussion, with a third reviewer consulted if necessary.

For each included study, data on the following aspects were extracted: study objectives, dataset details, preprocessing methods, network architecture, training strategy, evaluation metrics, and limitations. Based on their primary methodology, studies were grouped into three categories: CNN-based approaches, Vision Transformer approaches, and hybrid methods.

Figure 1 shows the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram that outlines how the studies were selected for this systematic review. A total of 6,050 records were identified from various databases and other sources. After removing duplicates, 4,200 records remained for screening, out of which 3,900 were excluded because they did not meet the inclusion criteria. Next, 300 full-text articles were reviewed for eligibility, but 275 were excluded for reasons such as being unrelated to the topic, having weak experimental designs, or lacking complete data. In the end, 25 studies were included in the qualitative phase of the systematic review.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram

III. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

A. Overview of Selected Studies

A total of 25 studies published between 2019 and 2025 met the eligibility requirements. These included CNN-only models, Transformer-based models, and hybrid approaches applied to brain tumor analysis using MRI datasets. Table I summarizes each study’s objective, methodology, performance, and noted limitations.

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S/N	Authors	Objective	Methodology	Results	Limitations
1	Bathe et al. (2021) [1]	To develop a novel approach for brain tumor detection	The research utilized a Depthwise Separable Convolutional Neural Network along with machine learning techniques like KNN and SVM, and their effectiveness was assessed using a Kaggle dataset that comprised 253 MRI images.	Depthwise Separable CNN attained an accuracy rate of 92%, surpassing the performance of machine learning models.	The model might experience overfitting if the dataset was not properly preprocessed. It is important to employ a more efficient algorithm that requires less computational time.
2	Vankdothu and Hameed (2022) [2]	To develop an automated system for tumor detection	The authors performed data preprocessing using an adaptive filter, and features were extracted with the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix; image segmentation was performed with the K-means algorithm, and recurrent neural network was utilized for tumor classification.	The model achieved 95.17% accuracy for brain tumor classification.	The technique employed is Computationally intensive, requires. There is need to use a more efficient algorithm to improve model robustness
3	Prasad et al. (2021) [3]	To diagnose brain tumor from MRI images using deep learning methods	Performance evaluation of CNN and machine learning algorithms was evaluated such as Logistic Regression and SVM.	CNN achieved higher detection accuracy than Machine learning algorithms.	There is Lack of data augmentation which may reduced robustness.
4	Shelatkar et al. (2022) [4]	To design an efficient deep learning framework for brain tumor detection	YOLOv5 deep learning algorithm was applied on BRAT 2021 dataset obtained from RSNA-MICCAI brain tumor	The model Achieved 88% precision in tumor detection.	Dataset imbalance, risk of overfitting without augmentation. There is need to perform data augmentation to addressed issues such as data imbalancing in the dataset used, to enhance generalization across different medical institution and reduce overfitting
5	Kibriya et al. (2020) [5]	To combine the learned features from one or more pre-trained model of CNNs	Features extracted from pre-trained deep CNN models such as AlexNet, GoogLeNet, and	The model achieved accuracy of 99.7%; for tumor classification.	Due to High-dimensional features fusion there may be risk of overfitting which need to be addressed to reduce the

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		for accurate tumor detection	ResNet18 were combined into a single feature vector, which was then used as input for Support Vector Machine (SVM) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifiers to perform tumor classification on 15,320MRI images		computational complexity of the model.
6	Afshar et al. (2019) [6]	To classify brain tumors using Capsule Networks	Capsule Networks an advanced neural network model was trained on brain tumor Figshare dataset.	The model Achieved 86.56% accuracy, outperforming CNN baseline.	The model Training time is computationally intensive, indicating the need for additional hyperparameter optimization to improve performance.
7	Reddy et al. (2024) [7]	To investigate the performance of fine tuned vision transformer models with deep learning models.	The study conducted performance evaluation of Fine-Tuned Vision Transformer models (FTVTs)—FTVT-b16, FTVT-b32, FTVT-116, FTVT-132 with deep learning models such as ResNet50, MobileNet-V2, and EfficientNet - B0 using a dataset with 7,023 images	FTVT-116 model achieved a noteworthy accuracy of 98.70% that other algorithms	There is need for model interpretability, to enable physician to gain more insights.
8	Ge et al. (2020) [8]	To improve brain tumor prediction using a deep semi-supervised learning framework	The authors utilized a deep semi-supervised learning approach combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with a graph-based learning framework which was evaluated on two brain tumor dataset: TCGA and MICCAI.	The model achieved: 86.53% accuracy on the TCGA dataset and 90.70% accuracy on the MICCAI dataset for tumor classification.	The study focuses only on glioma tumors (not all brain tumor types), limiting broader applicability
9	Sajjad et al. (2019) [9]	To develop a multi-grade brain tumor classification framework	The study employed CNN for both tumor segmentation and classification.	The model attained 96.56% accuracy for tumor classification	Segmentation errors may propagate to classification stage, thereby reducing the overall diagnostic accuracy of the system if the process was not efficiently addressed

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10	Kumar et al. (2024) [10]	To evaluate the performance of machine learning algorithms in brain tumor classification.	The study evaluates the performance of six machine learning algorithms: Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, Naïve Bayes, and Decision Tree and compared the performance of three feature extraction methods: Image Loading, Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG), and Local Binary Pattern (LBP) on brain tumor dataset sourced from kaggle.	Random forest attained the utmost prediction accuracy when used with extracted features for tumor detection.	Transfer learning may not generalize to large clinical data.
11	Salari et al. (2023) [11]	To examine the overall global prevalence of different types of primary central nervous system (CNS) tumors.	The authors carried out a systematic review of brain tumor detection system following the PRISMA 2020 guidelines using 80 selected studies.	The study showed that brain tumors contain 70.9% of all primary CNS tumors thereby making them the most prevalent disease .	Limited recent data was included in the study which may not reflect recent data statistics
12	Xie et al. (2022) [12]	To evaluate the performance of recent studies that utilized Convolutional Neural Networks for brain tumor classification using MRI images.	The authors conducted a systematic literature review on 83 studies related to CNN based techniques that was used for tumor detection	Result showed that CNN-based methods achieved high performance across many studies and clinically relevant for efficient tumor detection	There is lack of standardized benchmarks thereby making comparison across various studies difficult.
13	Gómez-Guzmán et al. (2025) [13]	To assessed the performance of pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks and Vision Transformer models for multi-class brain tumor classification	The study used Brain Tumor MRI dataset containing 7,023 MRI images which was tested on deep learning architectures: DeiT3_base_patch16_224, Xception41, Inception_v4, and Swin_Tiny_Patch4_Window7_224, using transfer learning.	Swin_Tiny_Patch4_Window7_224 model achieved the highest accuracy of 99.24% for tumor detection.	The study used a single publicly available dataset (Msoud), which may limit generalizability to other real-world clinical data sources.

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14	Balaji and Kirty (2022) [14]	To classify brain tumors using deep convolutional neural networks	The study employed four CNN architectures based on Transfer Learning for brain tumor detection using a dataset consisting of 3,264 2-D MRI images	EfficientNetB0 model achieved the utmost accuracy of 97.61%, outperforming other CNN architectures for tumor classification	The study considered only a limited number of tumor types
15	Chen et al., (2024) [15]	To develop a robust brain tumor classification model using a deep feature fusion approach that combines multiple pre-trained CNN architecture for enhancing diagnostic performance	The study used Figshare and Kaggle dataset and features were extracted using CNN pretrained models. Classification was then performed using the fused feature sets for model robustness	The feature fusion approach improved model generalization and reduced overfitting compared to single-model performance.	The approach is more computational intensive
16	Alsubai et al. (2022) [16]	To develop a hybrid deep learning model for brain tumor detection and classification from MRI images.	The Study utilized CNN–LSTM hybrid model for automatic classification of brain tumors	The proposed model achieved 99.1% accuracy suitable for tumor detection.	The dataset size and diversity were not specified which may lead to model overfitting
17	Buchade and Kantipudi. (2024) [17]	To analyze existing deep learning approached used for brain tumor detection from MRI images	The study conducted a comprehensive review of recent studies on brain tumor detection using hybrid deep learning approaches.	The review showed that hybrid models combining multiple architectures improve classification performance than traditional machine learning algorithms for tumor classifications	There is need for clinical acceptability and generalization of the models
18	Demiroğlu (2024) [18]	To apply Vision Transformer for brain tumor classification	The authors combined Vision Transformer (ViT) model to brain MRI images to extract deep visual features which was then fed into classical classifiers (SVM, Tree, and k-NN) to perform tumor classification.	The hybrid approach outperformed standalone ViT with 81.9% accuracy for tumor detection.	ere is need for more diverse dataset to improve model robustness

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19	Asiri et al. (2023) [19]	To Improve the classification accuracy of brain tumor detection	Performance evaluation of five pre-trained Vision Transformer models such as R50-ViT-116, ViT-116, ViT-132, ViT-b16, and ViT-b32 was conducted.	ViT-b32 achieved the highest classification accuracy of 98.24%, outperforming other ViT architectures	There is need to improve the generalizability of the model by using a more dataset
20	Martín and Sánchez (2025) [20]	To evaluate the performance of Vision Transformer (ViT) architectures in medical diagnostics	The paper used a Vision Transformer architectures consisting of Swin Transformer and MaxViT whose performance was evaluated on multi organl brain tumor dataset consisting of MRI and CT scans	Swin Transformer achieved 99.43% classification accuracy showing the effectiveness of mult organl on brain tumor diagnosis	The approach is computationally intensive.
21	Wang et al. (2024) [21]	To develop a hybrid model for staging and survival rate of tumor	Integration of a hybrid model consisting pf CNN and Transformer architecture for tumor diagnosis was conducted	The integration of CNN-Transformer architecture outperform single CNN model in tumor classifications..	There is need for model interpretability to enhanced clinical decision making.
22	Shobayo and Saatchi (2025) [22]	To assess the performance of deep learning models in medical imaging	Systematic review of existing studies on deep learning techniques was conducted	The findings showed that deep leaning achieved a remarkable accuracy in medical imaging diagnosis	There is limited quantitative meta analysis in the study.
23	Wang and Li (2025) [23]	To evaluate the performance of machine learning and deep learning models on BRATS datasets	The study evaluates the performance of random forest and deep learning architectures to optimized model performance using BRATS 2024 datasets	Random forest outperformed deep learning models in tumor classification with the highest accuracy of 87%.	There is need for more hyper-parameters tuning to improve deep learning prediction
24	Dawood et al. (2023) [24]	To improve the efficiency of brain tumor segmentation	The authors proposed a 3D framework using BRATS 2020 dataset for segmentation and Neurofeedback for skull stripping. Residual attention mechanisms in U-Net was used and dice similarity score	The model achieved DSC scores between 0.9961–0.9985, outperforming existing models.	There is need for more diverse dataset to improve tumor segmentation

			was used to evaluate model performance		
25	Hosny and Mohammed (2025), [25]	To review deep learning methods (2020–2024) for brain tumor detection and classification	Survey of studies on Brain tumor detection using BraTS and Figshare datasets.	CNNs and hybrid models perform best; ViTs and explainable AI show emerging promise.	lack of interpretability of the model still exist

B. CNN-Based Models

CNNs remain the most widely used networks for brain tumor tasks, as they are highly effective at extracting multi-level features from MRI scans. Many studies using CNNs reported classification accuracies exceeding 90% when tested on curated datasets like BRATS and institutional MRI collections [12], [13].

Common strategies included:

- i. Transfer learning with pretrained models such as ResNet, VGG16, and AlexNet [14].
- ii. Feature fusion to combine outputs from multiple CNNs for better prediction [15].
- iii. Hybrid CNN frameworks that used recurrent networks or ensembles to enhance robustness, especially with smaller datasets [16].

Challenges noted included overfitting in limited datasets, reduced cross-institution generalizability, and high computational demands [17].

C. Vision Transformer (ViT) Approaches

More recent studies have explored Vision Transformers (ViTs), which use self-attention to capture long-range dependencies in MRI data. Several ViT-based models reported results comparable to, or even better than, CNNs in classification and segmentation tasks [18], [19].

Notable findings include:

- a. Pretrained Transformer backbones like ViT-b32 and RanMerFormer achieved >95% accuracy on certain datasets [20].
- b. ViTs excelled in modeling global spatial relationships, a key advantage for tumors with irregular shapes and appearances.

However, their main drawback is computational cost, as self-attention grows quadratically with image size, raising scalability concerns [21].

D. Hybrid Approaches

Hybrid architectures combined CNNs with other models such as LSTMs or ensemble classifiers [22]. In some cases, CNNs handled local feature extraction while Transformers captured global context. These pipelines often showed greater robustness, though they required more resources to train and deploy.

E. Dataset Diversity and Preprocessing

The BRATS dataset was the most frequently used benchmark due to its multimodal MRI scans with expert annotations.

Other works relied on institutional or Kaggle datasets, though variations in imaging protocols limited cross-study comparability [23].

Preprocessing typically involved skull stripping, normalization, noise reduction, and segmentation. Data augmentation techniques such as flipping, rotation, and elastic transformations helped counter class imbalance [24]. Despite these measures, limited dataset diversity remained a major bottleneck.

F. Computational Demands

Both CNNs and ViTs were resource-intensive. Deep CNNs required high GPU memory and training time, while ViTs were even more demanding due to attention operations [25]. Approaches such as pruning, quantization, and lightweight Transformer variants have been proposed, but their adoption in neuro-oncology remains limited.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

A. Methodological Insight

The studies reviewed confirm that deep learning has significantly advanced brain tumor detection and segmentation in MRI analysis. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs) have emerged as the most prominent models. CNNs remain the benchmark due to their ability to learn hierarchical image features that capture both local and structural details, consistently achieving high accuracy across classification and segmentation tasks. Conversely, ViTs though relatively new, have demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in modeling long-range dependencies that CNNs typically overlook. When trained on large and diverse datasets, ViTs often achieve comparable or even superior results to CNNs, underscoring their potential for addressing the complex variability inherent in brain tumor imaging.

B. Dataset Limitations and Generalizability

A major challenge across the reviewed studies lies in dataset limitations. Public repositories such as the Brain Tumor Segmentation (BraTS) dataset provide valuable multimodal MRI scans, yet they fail to fully represent real-world variability in imaging protocols, tumor histology, and scanner hardware. Institutional datasets, while sometimes more diverse, often lack external validation, leading to overfitting and poor generalization in real-world scenarios. To overcome these challenges, future research should prioritize multi-

institutional collaborations, domain adaptation, and advanced data augmentation strategies. Such measures would enhance model robustness and ensure that AI systems can perform reliably across different clinical environments.

C. Computational Complexity

Despite their accuracy, both CNNs and ViTs require substantial computational power, posing barriers to clinical deployment. CNNs become increasingly resource-intensive as network depth increases, while ViTs demand even greater resources due to the quadratic scaling of their attention mechanisms. Although efficient alternatives such as MobileNet, EfficientNet, and lightweight Transformers have been proposed, they remain underexplored in brain tumor imaging. Optimizing model compression, efficient training pipelines, and edge-device deployment could help bridge the gap between high-performance AI research and practical clinical application.

D. Interpretability and Clinical Integration

Interpretability remains a critical concern for clinical adoption. Current deep learning models are often criticized as “black boxes,” offering limited insight into how predictions are derived. Several studies have attempted to improve transparency through visualization tools such as heatmaps, saliency maps, and attention overlays that highlight influential tumor regions. While these techniques enhance explainability, they lack standardization and have not been widely validated. Moreover, few AI models have undergone multi-center clinical trials, limiting confidence in their clinical reliability. For successful integration into routine workflows, future research must prioritize explainable AI (XAI) frameworks and rigorous real-world testing to ensure both trust and safety.

E. Comparative Advantages of CNNs and ViTs

At present, CNNs dominate the domain due to their architectural maturity, moderate computational needs, and the availability of well-established pretrained models. However, ViTs offer distinct advantages when trained on large datasets, as their self-attention mechanisms excel in capturing global spatial relationships. Emerging hybrid architectures that combine CNNs’ strong local feature extraction with ViTs’ contextual reasoning capabilities are showing promising results. These hybrid models may represent the next frontier in brain tumor imaging, balancing efficiency, accuracy, and generalizability especially when dealing with heterogeneous MRI data.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This review synthesized recent progress in applying CNN and ViT architectures to brain tumor detection using MRI. Evidence from 25 studies published between 2019 and 2025 shows that CNNs remain the most widely adopted models, consistently delivering high performance across tumor classification and segmentation tasks. ViTs, on the other

hand, have demonstrated substantial promise particularly when trained on large and complex datasets owing to their superior ability to model long-range dependencies.

Despite these achievements, several limitations persist. Dataset diversity remains insufficient, computational demands are high, and model interpretability is limited. Furthermore, the absence of extensive multi-institutional and real-world validation restricts the generalizability of current findings.

a. Recommendations for Future Research

To strengthen the applicability and impact of deep learning in neuro-oncology, future investigations should focus on the following areas:

1. Dataset Expansion and Diversity: Develop large-scale, multi-institutional MRI datasets that capture variations in imaging conditions, tumor types, and patient demographics to improve model generalization.
2. Model Efficiency: Design lightweight and resource-efficient CNN and ViT architectures that can be implemented in low-resource clinical environments without sacrificing diagnostic accuracy.
3. Interpretability and Trust: Incorporate explainable AI methods that provide transparent decision pathways to enhance clinician confidence and accountability in AI-assisted diagnostics.
4. Clinical Validation: Conduct prospective, multi-center trials and establish standardized evaluation benchmarks to assess the real-world performance of AI models.

By addressing these gaps, future systems can effectively merge CNNs’ robust feature extraction with ViTs’ powerful contextual reasoning, creating reliable, interpretable, and clinically deployable diagnostic tools. Such advancements will contribute to the progress of brain tumor detection and, ultimately, to improved patient care outcomes.

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